

Research Article

Phytoconstituents obtained from Tanzanian medicinal plants display a high potential to inhibit Glucosamine-6-phosphate synthase as an antimicrobial target

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Abstract: Recent pharmacological research has focused attention on biological properties of bioactive compounds derived from medicinal plants. With the aid of *in silico* modeling and computational studies, the possible antimicrobial activity of phytoconstituents isolated from various Tanzanian medicinal plants was investigated. Out of the eighteen compounds selected and docked against a critical antimicrobial target, Glucosamine-6-phosphate synthase from *Escherichia coli* (*E. Coli*), eight (8) compounds including baphikinone, annonaine, rheediaxanthone B, isorheediaxanthone, forbexanthone, amaniensine, 12-hydroxy-des-D-garcigerrin A and baphikixanthone showed high binding affinity towards the enzyme. The molecular interaction, in comparison with the reference compounds, fructose-6-phosphate and fluconazole revealed that the compounds favorably docked on the binding site and the enzyme-ligand complex possessed low binding energy value, implying that the compounds may be potent inhibitors of the enzyme. The binding energy values obtained ranged from -7.0 kcal/mol to -9.3 kcal/mol compared to -7.6 kcal/mol and -6.0 kcal/mol obtained for fluconazole and fructose-6-phosphate respectively. The compounds penetrated and appeared to completely blocked the active site and, engaged amino acid residues at the active site in strong hydrogen bonds. These residues include Val-399, Thre-352, Glu-488, Ser-349, Gln-348, Thre-302, Ala-602, Lys-603, and Ser-303 most of which are required for catalytic activity. Hydrophobic interaction also seemed to participate in stabilizing the enzyme-ligand complex. Overall, the binding affinity and configuration for the selected phytoconstituents were comparable to the control ligands. Hence, the compounds may competitively hinder the synthesis of glucosamine-6-phosphate that is required for bacterial and fungal cell wall production. The results obtained in this study validate the antimicrobial potential of the medicinal plant sources of the compounds and show that they possess the ability to inhibit glucosamine-6-phosphate synthase as a target while providing insights into the possible molecular interaction involved in the antimicrobial effects observed in earlier reported wet experiments.

INTRODUCTION

The Glucosamine-6-phosphate synthase (GlmS), an enzyme that plays a key role in the synthesis of the bacterial and fungal cell wall, has become a potential clinical target for antibacterial and antifungal drug discovery [1, 2]. The enzyme catalyzes a reaction between fructose-6-phosphate (F6P) and L- glutamine to generate glucosamine-6-phosphate that results in the production of UDP-N acetylglucosamine which is an essential component in building the peptidoglycan layer of bacterial and fungal cell walls [2, 3]. Thus, inhibition of this enzyme with chemical compounds will eventually result in the death of bacteria and fungi [4]. Therefore, it is not surprising to observe that some GlmS inhibitors both from natural or synthetic origin possess bactericidal or fungicidal properties [5]. On the other hand, the resistance

of pathogenic microorganisms to current antibiotics, anxiolytics, hypnotics, anticonvulsants, and sedatives is rapidly becoming the first challenge worldwide. The abuse of available synthetic antibiotics is a contributory factor to the increased incidence of microbial resistance to present day antibacterial and antifungal drugs. Meanwhile, prime and opportunistic bacterial and fungal infections are observed on an increasing trend because of the increased number of immune-compromised patients [6]. One of the essential ways of combating this new challenge is to discover novel and structurally diverse antibiotic compounds preferably from natural sources considering their reduced toxicity and side effects [3, 7, 8]. Although it is a fact that the enzyme is also found in mammals, there are substantial variations in physiological consequences of GlmS inhibition between microorganisms and mammals which form a stable

molecular basis for selectivity in action and toxicity of specific enzyme inhibitors [9].

To date, medicinal plants have proved to be a rich source of promising and exciting structures for drug discovery [8]. Some medicinal plants are known to possess pharmacological abilities to combat disease-causing pathogens [10, 11]. For decades, various plant extracts were studied for their antimicrobial properties against microorganisms such as bacteria (*Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus spp*, *Klebsiella pneumonia*, etc.) and some common fungi (*Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus niger*). Recently, the phytochemicals from such plant extracts with antifungal and antibacterial effects have been isolated and characterized [12-14]. Hence, attention has been diverted to studying their biological effect for various beneficial clinical and therapeutic applications.

In Tanzania, diverse group of compounds such as lactones, flavonoids, alkaloids, coumarins, limonoids, terpenoids, benzophenones, xanthenes and other compounds has been obtained from available medicinal plants. The plant species include *Baphia spp*, *Garcinia spp*, *Annona spp*, *Mammea spp*, *Teclea spp*, *Harrisonia spp*, etc. The reported biological properties of these plants are antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-HIV, antimalarial, anticancer, antifungal and larvicidal activities. The extracts of these plants are said to exhibit significant activities against a wide range of microorganisms [15]. Although the antimicrobial capacities of the extracts of these plants have been reported in *in vitro* experiments, the target and molecular mechanism of such properties remained unknown. Therefore, this research was done to elucidate the possible molecular basis of antimicrobial effects of selected compounds previously isolated from the Tanzanian medicinal plants.

Table 1. Selected phytoconstituents used as ligand in this study and their plant source

S/No	Name	Structure	Plant source	Plants part	Reference
1	Annonaine		<i>Annona Squamosal</i>	Leaves	15, 16
2	Tecleamaniensine B		<i>Teclea amanuensis</i>	Stem	17
3	Amaniensine		<i>Teclea amanuensis</i>	Stem	17
4	Baphikixanthenes A		<i>Baphia kirkii</i>	Stem	18

5	Baphikixanthones B		<i>Baphia kirkii</i>	Stem	18
6	Baphikixanthones C		<i>Baphia kirkii</i>	Stem	18
7	Baphikinone		<i>Baphia kirkii</i>	Stem	18
8	Garceduxanthonone		<i>Garcinia edulis</i>	Root	19
9	Forbexanthonone		<i>Garcinia edulis</i>	Root	19
10	Isorheedixanthonone B		<i>Garcinia volkensii</i>	Stem	20, 21, 22
11	12-hydro-des-D-garcigerrin A		<i>Garcinia volkensii</i> , <i>Garcinia livingstonei</i>	Stem	23

12	Rheediaxanthone B		<i>Garcinia volkensii</i>	Stem	22, 24, 25
13	3-hydroxy-5-methoxy biphenyl		<i>Allanblackia ulugurensis</i>	Stem	26, 27, 28
14	3-Methoxy-8,9-methylenedioxypterocarpene		<i>Baphia puguensis</i>	Root	15
15	4-hydroxy-3-methoxy cinnamate		<i>Baphia puguensis</i>	Root	29
16	Puguflavanone A		<i>Baphia puguensis</i>	Root	29
17	Puguflavanone B		<i>Baphia puguensis</i>	Root	29
18	Erythrinenegalone		<i>Baphia puguensis</i> , <i>Erythrina fusca</i>	Root	29, 30, 31

METHODS

Preparation of ligands

A total of twenty (20) ligands used for docking study were selected from the literature [15]. Out of these compounds, eighteen (18) were phytochemicals isolated from various medicinal plants found in Tanzania while the other two (2) ligands were fluconazole (a synthetic compound) and fructose-6-phosphate (natural ligand) which were used as reference compounds (Table 1). The chemical structure of these compounds was obtained from NCBI PubChem compound database (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pccompound>) and prepared using MarvinSketch. Three-dimensional (3D) optimizations of the ligand structures were done before use in docking studies. The 3D structure of the ligands was saved as MOL SD format after optimization. These were docked into refined GlmS model using "LigandFit" in the AutoDock 4.2.

Selection and preparation of protein structure through homology modeling

The starting three-dimensional structure of the protein (GlmS) utilized in this study was downloaded from the RCSB protein data bank (<http://www.rcsb.org>) with PDB ID: 2VF5. The macromolecule was found to be in complex with glucosamine-6-phosphate. The "FASTA" files (Accession: 2VF5_X GI:169404650) for this protein was obtained from www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed and was employed in homology modeling of the protein as done on the Swiss Model Server (<http://swissmodel.expasy.org>). The coordinate file of the template from protein data bank was used to model the 3D

structure of GlmS. All water molecules and ligand crystallized with the proteins were deleted before molecular docking procedures.

Evaluation and validation of the model

The modeled enzyme was assessed by procheck for structural analysis. The Ramachandran plot and Z score values were generated using the protein structure and model assessment tools of Pdbsum database of the European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI) (<http://www.ebi.ac.uk/>) and the Swiss-Model workspace (<http://swissmodel.expasy.org>). The protein structure was also loaded on ProQ web server to evaluate the PDB structure [32, 33]. The values for LG-score, Maxsub, as well as Qmean score, were obtained.

Molecular docking

For molecular docking analysis, Autodock vina 4.2 was used in this study [34]. All optimized ligand molecules were docked into the active site of refined GlmS. The rotatable bonds of the ligands were set to be free however the protein molecules were treated as a rigid structure. Throughout this *in silico* experiment, the grid parameters were set at x=60, y=60 and z=60 while the coordinate of origin was set at 12.61, 36.05 and 72.32 (x, y, and z) to include all the amino acid residues at the binding site while the spacing between grid points was kept at 0.375 angstroms. Ten (10) docking runs were performed for each compound with the number of modes set to 10 to achieve more accurate and reliable results.

Table 2. Binding energy values and hydrogen bond interaction between GlmS and the pure chemical compounds

Compound	E-value (Kcal/mol)	No of H-bond	Interactions with amino acid residue	Distance (Å)
Annonaine	-8.7	2	Val-399 (O--H-N)	3.31
			Lys-603 (N-H--O)	3.25
Tecleamaniensine B	-7.2	3	Thr-302 (O-H--O)	3.08
			Thr-302 (N-H--O)	2.86
			Thr-352 (O-H--O)	2.72
Amaniensine	-8.3	3	Gln-348 (O--H-N)	3.13
			Ser-303 (O-H--O)	3.24
			Ser-303 (O-H--O)	2.85
Baphikixanthonos A	-7.5	3	Thr-302 (O-H--O)	2.84
			Lys-603 (N-H--O)	3.13
			Val-399 (O-H--O)	3.07
Baphikixanthonos B	-7.9	3	Gln-348 (N-H--O)	3.20
			Ser-303 (O-H--O)	2.70
			Thr-302 (O-H--O)	3.26
Baphikixanthonos C	-9.0	1	Thr-302 (O-H--O)	2.87

Garceduxanthone	-7.6	2	Thr-302 (O-H--O)	2.94
			Thr-302 (N-H--O)	3.00
Forbexanthone	-8.4	2	Ser-303 (O-H--O)	3.30
			Ser-347 (O-H--O)	3.18
Isorheediaxanthone B	-8.5	5	Thr-352 (O-H--O)	3.10
			Glu-488 (O-H--O)	3.20
			Val-399 (O-H--O)	2.88
			Val-399 (O-H--O)	2.70
			Lys-603 (N-H--O)	2.86
12-hydro-des-D-garcigerrin A	-7.8	4	Thr-302 (N-H--O)	3.27
			Thr-302 (N-H--O)	2.80
			Thr-302 (O-H--O)	3.07
			Val-605 (N-H--O)	2.99
Rheediaxanthone B	-8.5	4	Val-399 (O-H--O)	3.15
			Val-399 (O-H--O)	2.71
			Lys-603 (N-H--O)	2.81
			Thr-352 (O-H--O)	2.99
3-hydroxy-5-methoxy biphenyl	-7.0	4	Ser-303 (O-H--O)	3.20
			Ser-347 (O-H--O)	3.18
			Gln-348 (N-H--O)	3.10
			Lys-603 (O-H--O)	3.27
3-Methoxy-8,9-methy lenedioxypterocarpene	-7.7	3	Thr-352 (O-H--O)	2.78
			Ser-349 (O-H--O)	3.28
			Ser-303 (O--O-H)	3.10
4-hydroxy-3-methoxy cinnamate	-7.1	6	Ser-349 (N-H--O)	2.85
			Ser-349 (O-H--O)	2.76
			Ser-347 (O-H--O)	3.20
			Ser-347 (O-H--O)	2.82
			Thr-352 (O-H--O)	2.92
			Thr-302 (O-H--O)	2.71
Baphikinone	-9.3	6	Ser-349 (N-H--O)	2.81
			Ser-349 (O-H--O)	2.76
			Ser-347 (O-H--O)	2.69
			Ser-347 (O-H--O)	3.07
			Thr-302 (O-H--O)	2.94
			Thr-302 (O-H--O)	3.11
Puguf flavanone A	-8.1	5	Ser-347 (O-H--O)	3.16
			Ser-349 (N-H--O)	3.29
			Ser-349 (O-H--O)	2.98
			Thr-352 (O-H--O)	3.08
Puguf flavanone B	-7.6	1	Thr-302 (O-H--O)	2.88
Erythrisenegalone	-8.7	5	Thr-352 (O-H--O)	3.13
			Ser-347 (O-H--O)	2.84
			Ser-349 (O-H--O)	2.79
			Ser-349 (N-H--O)	2.95
			Ala-602 (O-H--O)	2.86

Fluconazole	-7.6	3	Lys-603 (N-H--N)	3.13
			Ser-302 (N-H--O)	3.15
			Ser-347 (N-H--O)	3.16
Fructose-6-phosphate	-6.0	8	Ser-349 (O-H--O)	2.92
			Ser-349 (N-H--O)	3.11
			Thr-352 (O-H--O)	3.04
			Thr-352 (O-H--O)	3.20
			Ser-303 (O-H--O)	2.93
			Lys-603 (N-H--O)	3.18
			Thr-302 (O-H--O)	3.11
			Ser-347 (O-H--O)	2.78

Data analysis

All protein snapshots were taken using PYMOL while receptor-ligand molecular interaction was analyzed using Ligplot [35].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Since the inhibition of GlmS by a particular ligand suppresses the synthesis of bacterial and fungal cell wall which will significantly decrease the population of invading fungi and bacteria, the enzyme was selected as a target in this study to evaluate the antimicrobial potency of phytoconstituents obtained from important medicinal plants in Tanzania. The structure of GlmS, shown as cartoon representation, is given in Figure 1. The enzyme is known to contribute to the formation and maintenance of bacterial and fungal cell wall and has remained a validated target for antimicrobial drug discovery. In this study, docking experiment was performed using AutoDock 4.2 with PyMol Tool [36]. The binding energy values, interacting residues, number of hydrogen bond as well as the length of the bonds obtained from the docking experiment is summarized in Table 2 while the binding pose of the sample compounds in the active pocket is presented in Figure 2. The energy values ranged from -7.1 kcal/mol to -9.3 kcal/mol in comparison with the natural and synthetic reference compounds having binding energy values of -6.0 kcal/mol and -7.6 kcal/mol respectively. The binding affinity alone is not a sufficient tool to describe the enzyme-ligand complex stability. Therefore, molecular interactions such as hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic interactions of ligands were evaluated using Ligplot as shown in Figure 2. Among these compounds, the best eight (8) compounds with the high binding affinity towards the enzyme were selected for molecular interaction studies and compared with fluconazole (synthetic antibiotic) as well as fructose-6-phosphate (natural substrate).

Baphikinone, a compound isolated from the stem of *Baphia kirkii*, has the highest affinity with -9.3 kcal/mol energy value as compared to other compounds. This compound deeply penetrated into the substrate binding pocket on the enzyme (Figure 2; 1a) like the natural substrate, Fructose-6-phosphate (Figure 2; 2a) yielding a stable target-ligand complex. The binding pose of baphikinone at the active site is also similar to that of fluconazole, the control ligand (Figure 2; 3a) [2].

Figure 1. 3D model of E. Coli Glucosamine-6-phosphate synthase

Table 3. Ramachandran plot statistics of Glucosamine-6-phosphate synthase

Ramachandran Plot statistics	Glucosamine-6-phosphate synthase	
	No. of residues	Percentage
Most favoured regions [A,B,L]	501	93.5%*
Additional allowed regions [a,b,l,p]	33	6.1%
Generously allowed regions [~a,~b,~l,~p]	0	0.00%
Disallowed regions [XX]	2	0.4%
Non-glycine and non-proline residues	536	100.0%
End-residues (excl. Gly and Pro)	2	
Glycine residues	49	
Proline residues	21	
Total number of residues	608	

Table 4: Z-scores of QMEAN for individual component

Scoring function Term	Z-score (GlmS)
C _β interaction energy	0.39
All atom pairwise energy	0.37
Solvation energy	0.55
Torsion angle energy	0.27
Secondary structure agreement	0.23
Solvent accessibility agreement	0.77
Total Qmean-score	0.74
G-Factor value	-0.11
ProQ LG-score	8.05
ProQ Maxsub	0.66

QMEAN, qualitative model energy and ProQ score analysis

Fluconazole, a triazole antifungal agent, inhibits fungal growth by disrupting the fungal cell membrane and hence impairs cell replication [2]. The other compounds obtained from this plant (Baphikixanthonones A - C) also showed strong inhibitory potential on the enzyme with the binding energy value of -7.5 kcal/mol, -7.9 kcal/mol and 9.0 kcal/mol respectively. Baphikinone established 6 hydrogen bonds with residues Ser-349, Ser-347, Thr-302 and Thr-302. Some of these residues are essential for the binding of fructose-6-phosphate to GlmS (Table 2) and have been implicated in earlier reports of inhibition of the enzyme [3, 8]. Seven hydrophobic interactions surround baphikinone inside the binding pocket (Figure 2; 1b). The hydrogen bonds in conjunction with the hydrophobic interactions appeared to be responsible for the high inhibitory potential

of the compound on the enzyme [37]. The genus *Baphia* is often associated with antibacterial and antifungal bioactivities. The potency of *B. nitida*, *B. pubescens*, *B. bancoensis* and *B. massaiensis* various extracts against microbes have been previously documented [39 - 41]. The result of the current study lends credence to the possible antimicrobial properties of *Baphia kirkii* and the mechanism involved is probably via inhibition of GlmS. *Baphia kirkii* is also known for other pharmacological properties as its root decoction is drunk for epilepsy treatment in African countries [42]. Erythrisenegalone, a flavonoid isolated from *Baphia puguensis* root, also proved to be a potential antimicrobial compound with the binding energy value of -8.7 kcal/mol. This strong binding is likely associated with the existence of five hydrogen bonds established with residues Thr-352, Ser-347, Ser-349 and Ala-602 having the minimum bond length of 2.79 Å. The puguflavanone A and B which were also gotten from the root of the same plant displayed a high binding affinity with the enzyme recording -8.1 kcal/mol and -7.6 kcal/mol value respectively. They associated with the residues Ser-303, Ser-347, Ser-349 and Thr-352 (Table 2). These amino acid residues are essential for GlmS inhibition [4, 43]. These results suggest that these flavonoids possess antimicrobial potency and that the plant, *Baphia puguensis*, is a potentially good source of antimicrobial compounds. Flavonoids, as one of the bioactive compounds found in many medicinal plants, have numerous pharmacological properties including antifungal and antibacterial activities ascribed to them. Also, a large number of African medicinal plants including the *Baphia* species are commonly used in the treatment and cure of diseases occasioned by microorganisms.

1b

2a

2b

3a

3b

4

5

Fig 2. Molecular interaction between the compounds and GlmS

1. Baphikinone; 2. Fructose-6-phosphate C; 3. Fluconazole
 4. Annonaine; 5. Rheediaxanthone B; 6. Isorheediaxanthone B; 7. Forbexanthone; 8. Amaniensine; 9. 12-hydroxy-des-D-garcigerrin A; 10. Baphikixanthone. Molecular interactions depicted by LigPlot are mediated by hydrogen bonds and by hydrophobic interactions. Hydrogen bonds are represented by green dashed lines between the atoms in figures and hydrophobic contacts are shown in red arcs with spokes radiating towards the ligand atoms.

The isorheediaxanthone, forbexanthone and garceduxanthone are xanthone compounds gotten from *Garcinia edulis* root and stem. The plant is revered for its anti-HIV and anticancer effects [44]. Xanthenes are bioactive molecules for which diverse pharmacological activities have been reported including antimicrobial effect [45]. In this study, they showed binding energy value of -8.5 kcal/mol, -8.4 kcal/mol and -7.6 kcal/mol respectively. They formed hydrogen bonds with amino acid residues Ser-303, Ser-347, Thr-302, Val-399, Glu-488, Thr-352 and Lys-603 as can be seen in Table 2 [8]. Rheediaxanthone B and 12-hydro-des-D-garcigerrin A are also xanthenes with strong affinity to GlnS. Both were isolated from the stem of *Garcinia volkensii*. The genus *Garcinia* is known to comprise a group of medicinal plants with potential therapeutic agents. The various parts of fruit, stem, flower, bark, and leaves, etc. of the plants have been extensively used across the globe as an ethnomedicine to treat numerous disorders such as microbial infection, inflammation, cancer, oxidative stress and obesity [46]. With four hydrogen bonds to residues Val-399, Lys-603 and Thr-352, rheediaxanthone B exerts an inhibitory effect at the binding site of GlnS while 12-hydro-des-D-garcigerrin A associated with GlnS active site via hydrogen bonds with Thr-302 and Val-605. Xanthenes have been widely studied from diverse plant species for their potent antimicrobial properties [47 - 49].

Ramachandran Plot analysis of the receptor (GlnS)

Figure 3. Ramachandran plot generated by PROCHECK. Red areas correspond to favored region, allowed region are presented in yellow while light yellow areas correspond to generously allowed region and disallowed region is shown in white.

Annonaine, amaniensine and tecleamaniensine B are biologically active alkaloids from *Annona squamosa* leaves and *Teclea amaniensis* stem respectively. *Annona squamosa*

is said to exhibit antimicrobial, insecticidal, anti-tumor agent, antidiabetic, antioxidant, anti-lipidemic and anti-inflammatory in folkloric records while the antimycobacterial activity of *Teclea amaniensis* has been extensively reported [50 - 52]. Annonaine established two hydrogen bonds with Val-399 and Lys-603 while amaniensine formed the hydrogen bond with Gln-348 and Ser-303. The residues making hydrophobic contact with the compounds include Leu-601, Glu-488, Val-605, Cys-300, Thr-352 and Lys-603 [4].

In summary, amino acid residues Val-399, Thr-302, Ser-303, Thr-352, Gln 248, Ser-347, Ser-349, Lys-603, Glu-488, and Val-605 are essential for possible GlnS inhibition by chemical compounds isolated from Tanzanian medicinal plants [3-5, 8, 43, 53-55]. Interestingly, these compounds were previously assumed to be responsible for multiple anti-infective properties of the plants including antifungal, antileishmanial, antimalarial, antitrypanosomal, antibacterial, antitubercular and antiviral [44]. Hence, these results serve as useful validation the antimicrobial potential of these compounds and the medicinal plants containing them. To determine the quality of starting protein used for this experiment, the modeled GlnS protein was structurally assessed, and the achieved Ramachandran plot is presented in Figure 3. The plot statistics revealed that 99.6 percent of the residues are found in the allowed regions with 501 out of total 608 amino acid residues present in the most favored region, 33 residues in the allowed region and only 2 amino acid residues discovered in the disallowed region making 0.4 percent (Table 3). The obtained G-factor value was -0.11 while the LG-score, Maxsub value and total QMEAN-score for the model as obtained from ProQ analysis were 8.05, 0.66 and 0.74 respectively (Table 4). An LG-score value > 4 usually indicates that the model is extremely good while a Maxsub score of > 0.5 also shows that the protein is very good. From these parameters, the modeled protein was accepted as a suitable starting material for the docking study [56 - 58].

CONCLUSION

Based on the results obtained from this study, the selected phytochemicals found in Tanzanian medicinal plants displayed antimicrobial potentials and are likely responsible for the antibacterial and antifungal effects of the plants. Among all the compounds chosen for this research, baphikixanthone, annonaine, rheediaxanthone-B, isorheediaxanthone, forbexanthone, amaniensine, 12-hydroxy-des-D-garcigerrin A and baphikixanthone displayed a strong potential to inhibit Glucosamine-6-phosphate synthase. Accordingly, the molecular target for the antibacterial effects of these compounds is possibly Glucosamine-6-phosphate synthase; an enzyme required for cell wall synthesis. It is evident from the *in silico* experiments that these natural compounds exert some inhibitory effects on glucosamine-6-phosphate synthase competitively. Inhibition of this enzyme by the natural compounds may be responsible for the reduction in microbial loads as claimed in previous

researches. The enzyme inhibition is possibly useful because the compounds bind to the active site and predictably prevent substrate access to the catalytic site while the enzyme-inhibitor complexes were stabilized by hydrogen bonds and hydrophobic interactions. The natural compounds might provide chemical scaffolds for the design and development of efficient, optimal and potential antimicrobial agents that may be efficacious in the control of infections among humans.

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